

TYPES OF CORRUPTION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

Azimov Khairullo Gaibullaevich

**Investigator of the Denau District Department
Surkhandarya regional administration
Department for Combating Economic Crimes
at the Prosecutor General's Office
Republic of Uzbekistan, 2nd level lawyer
www.khayrullwolf@gmail.com
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ABSTRACT

In recent years, our country has been implementing significant organizational and legal reforms in the fight against corruption. Systemic measures are being taken to raise legal awareness and awareness among the population and foster a societal intolerance toward corruption.

Creating a society and state free from corruption will be a solid guarantee of the country's development. In his speech dedicated to the 26th anniversary of the Constitution, delivered on December 7, 2018, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: "We will never achieve our goal through corruption" [1].

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All state reforms aimed at combating corruption are carried out in the interests of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens.

Particular attention is paid to the development of an intolerant attitude towards corruption in the education system, and the training of competitive personnel with independent thinking and high moral and ethical qualities.

In particular, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020, the President noted: "We are obligated to create all the conditions for the education of our knowledge-seeking, energetic young people who want to obtain higher education and work on themselves. Therefore, in 2020, we will increase the coverage of high school graduates with higher education to at least 25%, and in the future to 50–60%" [2].

To deeply and accurately understand the structure of corruption in education, it is necessary to identify its causes and regulatory mechanisms. The education system can be corrupted in several ways, for example:

- through powers of authority related to training;
- through the supply of goods and services;
- as a result of unfair professional conduct;
- in the tax and property spheres [3].

Corruption affects all areas of planning and management: information systems, school construction, selection and appointment of teachers, their career advancement (including the incentive system), supply and distribution of equipment and textbooks, allocation of funds (scholarships, subsidies, etc.), conducting examinations, issuing certificates and diplomas, conducting extracurricular activities, and much more.

Corruption in education has various consequences. In particular:

- As in other sectors, corruption leads to the theft of financial resources;
- When unreasonable admission requirements are tightened, bribery in exams flourishes, the abilities of talented young people are misused, and corruption and favoritism among young people grows, the opportunities for pupils and students to obtain high-quality education are sharply reduced.

Such consequences are not typical for any other public sector.

They are closely intertwined with the core functions of the educational system, meaning that the corruption that gives rise to them is directly linked to education.

In terms of the number of employees (especially teachers) and the population served, education is the second-largest, if not the largest, public sector. Educational services are provided to families with preschool- and school-age children, young people, and anyone who chooses to pursue an education. This means that a very large number of people in the country suffer from the consequences of corruption in education. This situation makes corruption in this sector a particularly pressing political issue [1].

Unless citizens actively demand accountability from government and public institutions, tightening legislation and creating effectively managed institutions will not be enough to prevent corruption.

Indeed, moral education of students helps in the fight against corruption, since young people are the future of any state.

However, anti-corruption education cannot operate in isolation. The environment in which children and young people receive education has a decisive influence on their attitudes toward this issue. Therefore, efforts to change interactions and behavior must be integrated into moral education (especially among teachers and mentors). Improved governance and greater public oversight of those working in this field are essential.

Anti-corruption measures in education must encompass the entire educational environment. It is essential to create a system that values honesty and good governance, and ensures effective, transparent, and public oversight of the sector's operations and the spending of resources. When analyzing the problem of corruption in the education system, it is important to understand that citizens' attitudes toward public administration play a key role.

The weaknesses of the education system are:

- personnel,
- financing,
- government procurement.

With regard to personnel, potential vulnerabilities include imperfect legislation and fundamental management principles, which complicate the fight against corruption. Failure to ensure compliance with current legislation indicates a lack of transparency, oversight, and motivation for effective performance within the public administration system [3].

Potential weaknesses of the financial system include:

- lack of opportunities for reorganization of the system as a result of its decentralization,
- insufficient level of internal and external control.

Weaknesses of the public procurement system include:

- legal norms that do not comply with international standards for competitive and fair tendering and contracting,
- weak anti-corruption legislation and basic principles,
- ineffective internal and external control mechanisms, as well as complaint handling mechanisms.

Scientific literature emphasizes that corruption largely depends on:

- stability of political systems,
- the existing legal framework,
- openness and transparency of the media,
- the level of responsibility of individual officials and institutions,
- the effectiveness of existing governance mechanisms,
- as well as from the specifics of foreign investments [2].

Public corruption is the abuse of power by officials for personal gain. However, education is an important public good. Therefore, professional standards should not be reduced solely to the pursuit of material gain.

If a higher education institution has a negative reputation, if its faculty or administration accepts bribes for admission, grades, or diplomas, this has a negative impact on graduates' employment. While the risk of being unemployed is lower within the country, when applying to government institutions, in the private market, especially in international companies recruiting abroad, graduates from universities with questionable reputations can face serious problems.

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